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THE IMPACT OF KAHOOT ON YOUNG LEARNERS' READING COMPREHENSION: ACTION RESEARCH STUDY

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Abstract. This action research study examines how using Kahoot can support young EFL learners' reading comprehension and engagement. The study involved students aged 10–12 who completed ten Kahoot reading games over ten lessons. Quantitative results showed some improvement between the first and final games, but no consistent progress across all sessions. However, qualitative data revealed that Kahoot greatly increased students' motivation, participation, and willingness to read more carefully. Overall, the study suggests that while Kahoot may not immediately boost reading comprehension, it creates a more engaging classroom environment that encourages young learners to interact with reading texts more actively.

Key words: *Kahoot, Gamification, Young learners, Action Research, Reading Comprehension, Engagement.*

Introduction

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Reading remains one of the most challenging skills for young EFL learners, who often perceive reading tasks as boring, difficult, and disconnected from real learning. As a teacher working with learners aged 10–12, I observed reluctance, shallow comprehension, and reliance on memorization when engaging with reading passages. And many children and teenagers show little motivation and engagement in reading, a study conducted by Mullis I. V. S. et.al, point out that on average 40% of learners, from 50 countries reported being “somewhat” or “less than” engaged in reading classes (2016). Therefore, motivation is essential for activation of behavior as well as engagement since they are interrelated. Michael L. Kamil, et.al, point out that less motivated reader spends less time reading, has lower cognitive effort and less dedicated to full understanding of a particular passage than a highly motivated reader (2008).

Given learners’ playful nature and strong sense of competition, I explored whether **gamification**, specifically Kahoot, could make reading more engaging and support meaningful comprehension. Because in a gamified classroom, students have an opportunity to collaborate with their classmates in a system that was created to pull them out from conventional classroom settings, where they feel something new, exciting and motivated to learn and practice (Hanus and Cruz, 2018). Hung also points that learning through online games, in other words gamification motivates learners to see their own learning progress, interacting with their classmates in a classroom setting in a highly engaging and enjoyable way (2017).

This study was conducted as **action research**, as it “is a useful tool for change and improvement at a local level” (Louis C. et.al, 2018). The purpose was to find a practical solution to a classroom problem and improve teaching practices through iterative cycles.

Research question and objective

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What is the impact of incorporating Kahoot games into EFL classroom to engage young learners in reading activities?

To assess the influence of Kahoot on young learners' reading comprehension skills' improvement.

Participants

A group of young EFL learners (aged 10–12) from an after-school program studying at RIKS language center in Tashkent.

Action Research Design

This study followed the principles of **action research**:

- identifying a classroom problem,
- implementing an intervention,
- observing its effects,
- reflecting on improving future teaching.

Intervention

The intervention consisted of **10 Kahoot reading comprehension games** across 10 lessons.

Each game contained:

- 2 Gist questions,
- Several detail-focused questions, based on passages provided *without* titles to strengthen inference skills.

Data Collection

Quantitative: scores from all 10 Kahoot games.

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Qualitative: teacher observation and student group interview to understand participation, motivation, and behavior.

Discussions and conclusions

According to the quantitative results (first and last recorded scores) it can be concluded that students' gained score rose significantly, for example, the student 1 gained 4600 scores in the first game and 6038 in the last game. However, 10-day- game results did not show any stable improvement. The results of research conducted in Indonesia is consistent with the results of this research, it states that there was not any significant difference on students reading comprehension. The study was mixed research, to collect quantitative data quasi-experimental research design was carried out (Pahamzah, J., Syafrizal, S., and Nurbaeti, N. 2022).

In contrast, another research carried out in Indonesia with collaboration of schoolteachers and University students on the effect of vocabulary mastery and reading comprehension skills in class enriched with Kahoot showed that platform Kahoot impacted positively on students' performance. It was action research, which included 3 cycles, quantitative data was collected from pre and posttests after each cycle, it shows students increased academic performance in terms of reading and vocabulary (Marsa, C.S., Kuspiyah, H.R., Agustina, E. 2021).

Conclusion

The aim of this study was to address a problem which my young-aged students were facing, reading skills. This study played a significant role for me to deeply comprehend the nature of teaching young learners and to explore findings of my colleagues from different parts of the world. Although quantitative data results did not show a significant

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improvement regarding students' reading skills, qualitative data results prove that incorporation of Kahoot highly motivated students, which in turns engaged them in reading activities.

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